

Preprint: Representations of Economic Inequality and Welfare Redistribution in UK Mainstream Party Programs, 2005–2024.

Author Names:

Daniel Walsh, University Grenoble Alpes, CESICE
Sonja Zmerli, Sciences Po Grenoble UGA, CESICE

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1. Abstract

Despite significant economic inequality, demands for redistribution in the UK remain limited, challenging models that assume a self-maintaining relationship between inequality and public demand. This paper critically examines how political communications shape public perceptions of economic inequality and redistribution. Analysing British mainstream party manifestos from 2005 to 2024, we employ an exploratory mixed-methods design combining quantitative keyword frequency analysis with qualitative thematic analysis derived in a dynamic epistemology. Our findings reveal that political discourse often reifies economic inequality as 'equality of opportunity' and contextualizes it through individual life-course narratives. Moreover, political parties—particularly on the left—have politicized economic inequality to build group identities and raise concern without promoting trust in solutions. These findings suggest that public perceptions and demands are shaped by politicization processes, emphasizing the dynamic role of political communication in shaping public opinion.

2. Introduction

Classic models, such as the 'median voter' hypothesis (Meltzer & Richard 1981), provide frameworks for theorizing citizens' political behaviour toward economic inequality and

redistributive demands in democratic states (Kenworthy & McCall 2008). In these models, people are considered in generic terms, voting according to their economic self-interest. According to the ‘median voter’ hypothesis, at the micro-level, i.e. individual voters, economic inequality should lead more people to benefit from greater redistribution – thus incentivising more people to vote for parties favouring redistribution. However, at the macro-level, i.e. national, there is limited evidence supporting this simplistic model of political behaviour. Despite substantial evidence showing that economic inequality harms political, societal, and economic spheres (Stiglitz 2012; Schäfer & Schwander 2019), scholars continue to ask why high levels of income and wealth inequality do not necessarily lead to greater demands for redistribution (Choi 2019; Franetovic & Castello 2022; Haddon & Wu 2022; Reyes & Gasparini 2022; Schulz et al. 2022).

In this paper, we explore the impact of political communications that shape everyday thinking on economic inequality and redistribution, using British mainstream party programs from general elections between 2005 and 2024 as a case study. Drawing on theoretical and methodological tools from social representation and communication theories—alternative to standard approaches in public opinion (Marková 2023)—we make four key contributions to the literature. (1) The concept of ‘economic inequality’ is reified in political communication as ‘equality of opportunity.’ (2) In this reification, ‘economic inequality’ is not exclusively treated as disparities in the accumulation of income or wealth, as assumed by objective indicators. Instead, it is regularly rendered a concrete aspect of public understanding through individual life-course narratives, such as the progression from a working family to a dignified pensioner. (3) The salience of ‘economic inequality’ or the redistributive features of the welfare state in political communication are rarely directly linked in discourse. Instead, these concepts are indirectly related through their relevance to the experiences of valued or devalued social groups within society. (4) The salience of ‘economic inequality’ and the redistributive features of the

welfare state in political communication bears limited direct correlation with objective measures of economic inequality. Rather, the way these concepts are invoked reflects broader party strategies (e.g., positioning around the 2016 Brexit referendum).

In the remainder of this introduction, we will advance the theoretical-methodological foundations of this study, contrasting the epistemological differences between theories of social representation and communication with standard approaches in public opinion, with the British politics of economic inequality and redistribution as example.

Public Opinion

Gold-standard methods in social research, such as nationally representative sample surveys, assume that there is consensus across the sample population regarding the definition of the object under study—for example, economic inequality (Bauer & Gaskell 2008). However, perceptions of economic inequality may systematically vary among individuals, prompting researchers to focus on modelling measures of central tendency and dispersion to capture these variations (Willis et al. 2022). Researchers adopting this approach have compared subjective and objective measures of economic inequality, positing that divergences between these measures relate to a statistical inference problem: with access to limited samples of information, individual economic agents must infer their position for the entire income distribution (Cruces et al. 2013; Suss 2023).

In the 'median-voter' hypothesis (Meltzer & Richard 1981), people are assumed to hold up-to-date information on their objective position in the economic distribution enabling them to vote according to economic self-interest. Yet, scholarship has evidenced that perceptions of economic inequality may be biased in ways that reflect the reduced perceptual information that their situatedness in unequal economic distribution affords (Choi 2021; Hajdu 2024; Knell &

Stix 2020). Under conditions of high national economic inequality, as exemplified by the British case (Hauser & Norton 2017), common findings include: people overestimating the size of the middle class; low-income individuals overestimating their own economic position while high-income individuals underestimate theirs; low-income individuals predominantly perceiving the income distribution as right-skewed, whereas high-income individuals view it as left-skewed; and high-income individuals exhibiting lower subjective perceptions of inequality (Knell & Stix 2020).

Divergences between objective and subjective measures have been linked to socio-economic segregation, wherein societies with high levels of inequality tend to have people living in socio-economically segregated communities (Schulz et al. 2022; Suss 2023; Willis et al. 2022). This segregation limits opportunities for individuals to interact with and compare themselves to those who are either more or less affluent (Schulz et al. 2022; Willis et al. 2022). Changes in the media environment may afford little informational content on economic inequality to counteract the perceptual limitations of personal experience. From the 1980s onwards, the British media has progressively experienced liberalization and deregulation, in particular the Broadcasting Act 1990 and the Communications Act 2003—which resulted in less educational programming on economic inequality topics (Mack 2022).

Research suggests that people try to align their views of the current state of society with their beliefs about what a ‘fair’ society should be (Cavaillé 2023). In this context, support for the redistributive functions of the welfare state may not only be conditioned on economic self-interest, but as mechanisms to preserve the perceived ‘fairness’ of existing inequalities (Cavaillé 2023). For example, the British public often overestimate the size and relationship with middle class (Knell & Stix 2020). This overestimation can reflect beliefs in meritocracy, as representation of a large middle class may be seen as outcome of a fair system based on

education and hard work (Pereira et al. 2024). In addition, meritocratic beliefs may condition what is perceived as the ‘correct’ mechanism for redistribution (Orton & Rowlingson 2007), as the redistributive functions for the state may serve to create the conditions for individual advancements through education and work (Pereira et al. 2024). For example, in the UK, policies promoting ‘equality of opportunity,’ such as investments in education and healthcare, are more popular than those focused on ‘equality of outcome,’ like progressive taxation or welfare programs (Alesina et al. 2018; Benson et al. 2024).

When fairness is framed within a meritocratic belief system that emphasizes individual hard work, stigma holds a functional value for the public; it serves to maintain the distinction and valence between ‘deserving’ and ‘non-deserving’ groups, especially between the working and unemployed poor (Benson et al. 2024) or those categorized in policy as Not in Education, Employment, or Training (NEET) (McPherson 2021). The British liberal welfare regime, characterized by a strong reliance on the market, minimal state intervention, and means-tested benefits, frequently emphasizes individual responsibility, thereby fostering concerns about welfare dependency (Larsen 2013; Laenen 2020). A recurring theme in British political rhetoric has been the portrayal of social beneficiaries as ‘free riders’ (Cavaillé 2023), a narrative that gained momentum following the widening economic inequality triggered by the 2008 Global Financial Crash and the subsequent program of austerity (Berry 2022). Similarly, austerity measures introduced by the 2010–2015 coalition government were advanced through a narrative of ‘strivers’ versus ‘shirkers,’ reinforcing negative stereotypes about welfare recipients (Patrick 2014). Welfare reforms during the austerity period, such as the 2012 Welfare Reform Act, heightened the conditionality of benefit entitlements—both for in-work and out-of-work benefits—specifically targeting those classified as NEET (Wrigley 2024). Indeed, stigmatizing rhetoric towards the unemployed in British media tends to intensify during periods of rising unemployment, as observed during the 1980s (McArthur & Reeves 2019).

Theories of Social Representations and communication

In summary, scholarship in public opinion suggests that systemic perceptual biases play a crucial role in maintaining the status quo regarding perceptions of economic inequality and the British welfare state's role in addressing it; reinforced by fairness beliefs rooted in meritocratic ideals. Scholars have proposed that economic inequality creates conditions where individuals fail to recognize their actual position in the economic hierarchy and instils a belief in fairness that deviates from their objective economic self-interest. Furthermore, this system tends to cleave social groups and assign them value in relation to their contributions to- and dependency on- the welfare state.

In this paper, we propose that the alternative epistemological framework offered by the theory of social representations and communication (Marková 2023) can refine models of political behaviour concerning public opinion on economic inequality and demands for redistribution. Theories of social representation and communication are rooted in a dynamic relational epistemology (Marková 2023). We will discuss how this offers alternative interpretations related to motivation and group dynamics, drawing predominantly on literature of media representations. This sets the stage for the methods and empirical contributions made through this literature, which can refine approaches to elite political communications. As we will describe, rather than objective inequality inherently instilling conditions for its misrecognition and belief in its fairness (Gobel & Carvacho 2024), moments when economic inequality issues come to the forefront both elevate concern for the issue and serve to develop a political left and liberal oppositional grouping, while also discouraging structural redistribution.

Studies on public opinion towards economic inequality and redistribution often rely on a static unitary epistemology (Marková 2008). They assume individuals possess largely fixed

and unchanging principles and knowledge. This assumption enables measurement through UK programs such as the International Social Survey Programme (ISSP), the European Social Survey (ESS), and British Social Attitudes survey (BSA). These surveys regularly ask participants to evaluate the degree, causes, and desire for change regarding economic inequality. This approach allows correlations with factors like objective and perceived socio-economic status, gender, race, place of living, belief systems, ideologies, and political affiliation, guiding refinements and improvements in measurement (Bastias et al. 2024; Benson et al. 2021; Jachimowicz et al. 2023; Marandola 2021).

This unitary approach can be misleading because it assumes that perceptions of inequality, along with demands for redistribution, are self-perpetuating. According to this perspective, increasing objective inequality creates conditions that lead people to misrecognize it and believe in its fairness (Gobel & Carvacho 2024). However, this proposition is difficult to uphold when considering the intermittent nature of public concern and discourse about inequality, even though objective inequality has widened substantially since the 1980s and accelerated during the 2008 Global Financial Crisis. For instance, in the UK, despite sharp increases in objective inequality—as indicated by a more than 30% rise in the GINI coefficient between 1979 and 1992 (Smeeding 2005)—media concern about the issue fluctuated in waves. Public alarm over perceived economic inequality grew throughout the 1990s, peaking in 1998, and then declined until 2003 (McGovern et al. 2023). After this period of decline, the salience of economic inequality gradually increased, surging again between 2006–2008 and 2010–2015 prior to and following the 2008 financial crash, respectively (McGovern et al. 2023).

Instead of objective economic inequality directly influencing its recognition or non-recognition in society, it is more accurate to consider who speaks about economic inequality and how they do so, as this reflects what they aim to achieve in relation to competing

communicators in society. This concept is well-established in theories of social representation and communication (Foster 2011). While unitary theories describe individuals as motivated by assumed fixed and abstract factors (e.g., economic self-interest), dynamic epistemology emphasizes motivation as a relational feature (Marková 2008). Groups position themselves on issues conditionally in relation to social others (Marková 2008). In doing so, in-group and out-group identities, along with the object of representation, may be reconstituted in ways that affirm the groups' distinct motivations, potentially fostering both competition and cooperation (Foster 2011; Marková 2007).

For example, between 2010 and 2015, a coalescing group of political leftists and liberals advanced the recognition of economic inequality in society to develop their distinctive identity and position themselves against competing groups (Savage & Vaughan 2024). This period has been characterized as a "golden period" (Savage & Vaughan 2024, p. 184) for inequality discourse in the UK. Although the GINI coefficient peaked in 2008 during the Great Recession of 2008–2009, this did not initially trigger increased salience of economic inequality and actually stalled its recognition (McGovern et al. 2023). Instead, it enabled oppositional figures—especially from the political left and socially liberal circles, notably *The Guardian* newspaper and the Labour Party—to promote high-profile academic publications such as *The Spirit Level* by Richard Wilkinson and Kate Pickett in 2009, and the English translation of Thomas Piketty's *Capital in the Twenty-First Century* in 2014 (McGovern et al. 2023; Savage & Vaughan 2024). It is important to note that the media did not simply serve as a passive conduit for public education; from the 1990s onwards, scholarly economic literature on "income inequality" had already been growing exponentially (McGovern et al. 2023), substantially earlier than when these high-profile works were publicized through the media.

However, although this affirmed economic inequality as a distinctive concern of liberal and left-wing political groups in society (Savage & Vaughan 2024), their motivations extended beyond abstract moral philosophy to differences in political economy. From this perspective, what is motivating about fairness beliefs is not simply the abstract ideal but rather what this belief system can serve to the group that advances it (Cavaillé 2023; Chauhan & Foster 2014). For example, Savage and Vaughan (2024) point out that in the UK's discourse on inequality, Thomas Piketty's *Capital in the 21st Century* provided *The Guardian* with an opportunity to establish a distinctive role and identity in contrast to conventional business-oriented press like *The Times* and *The Daily Telegraph*, as reflected in the difference in salience economic inequality served during this period (McGovern et al. 2023).

Yet, while the attention given to economic inequality during this period partly enabled the formation of an oppositional group of left-wing politics and media consumption (Savage & Vaughan 2024), the way in which they did so did not necessarily engender calls for structural changes to bring about structural redistribution (McGovern et al. 2023). Instead, even when critiquing the unfairness of economic inequality, they framed it predominantly as an individual issue and maintained scepticism about possible structural changes, supporting divisions between the perceived deserving and undeserving of welfare (McGovern et al. 2023). For example, while Thomas Piketty was heralded as a "rock-star economist" in outlets like *The Guardian* (Guardian 2014) and seemed to gain positive acceptance on the surface, his arguments were regularly delegitimized even in these outlets (Grisold & Theine 2020). This delegitimization occurred by portraying his proposals as ideologically driven, associating them with figures of the hard left like Karl Marx (Grisold & Theine 2020). Metaphors from medicine and cooking were used to depict his "recipes" and "prescriptions" for inequality as "old" and "narrow-minded" (Grisold & Theine 2020). In some ways this is expected, as even under the New Labour government, the term 'redistribution' was considered taboo by commentators from

the Guardian (Lynch 2020), and more generally, economic inequality has long been treated in the media as an ideological concept compared to the perceived neutrality of poverty (Lugo-Ocando & Lawson 2022).

While the 2008 financial crisis may have heightened concern for economic inequality (Savage & Vaughan 2024), this concern did not translate into support for an expansion of the welfare state (Berry 2022). Between 2010 and 2015, the UK experienced what has been described as a "media monoculture" (Barnes & Hicks 2018, p. 344), where popular opinion, the media, and mainstream political parties aligned in emphasizing the need for collective "punishment" for the perceived excessive growth of the state under the pre-2010 New Labour government (Barnes & Hicks 2018; Berry 2022). Notably, the UK was an outlier in the duration of popular support for austerity measures, maintaining majority approval until 2015 (Berry 2022). Critics have observed that rhetoric during this period often sidelined or misinterpreted the dynamic effects of deficit reduction or expansion, particularly regarding economic growth. Discussions shifted to static media and political frames that portrayed the national deficit simply as the difference between income and expenditure (Barnes & Hicks 2018). This perspective frequently employed metaphors of household finances to promote fiscal restraint (Berry 2022).

The combination of a focus on individualized solutions to economic inequality among the liberal left and widespread support for austerity until 2015 contributed to the rise of so-called "poverty porn" television programming (Beresford 2016). During this time, there was a growing public appetite for "discovering" recipients of social welfare. These programs often drew on longstanding stereotypes of the unemployed poor as untrustworthy and undeserving due to perceived deficiencies in rationality, work ethic, and morality (Larsen 2013). Indeed, despite an apparent concern for economic inequality, there was also resistance to structural

change, which helps explain why the dissemination of superficially neutral information during this period on economic inequality did not engender calls for redistribution. The BBC, the most-used news source in the UK in 2013 (Ofcom 2013), was cautious about appearing partisan on issues of economic inequality. This led to ambiguity in discussing possible solutions to avoid being perceived as biased (Lugo-Ocando & Lawson 2022). As a publicly funded entity, the BBC presented economic inequality in explicitly neutral, quantitative terms (Savage & Vaughan 2024). For instance, the BBC's 2013 Great British Class Survey allowed over nine million Britons to determine their class status using a "class calculator." While the BBC was well-positioned to lead on "citizen science" initiatives due to its public funding (Savage & Vaughan 2024), the survey's conclusions were rendered "unserious" through gamification and failed to provide descriptions that connected inequality to lived experiences (Savage & Vaughan 2024). This is significant because it meant that abstract information on economic inequality was not linked to the real-life experiences of individuals within these categories (Savage & Vaughan 2024).

Since 2016, political momentum on addressing economic inequality has waned and fragmented, particularly as it became associated with setbacks like the defeats of Jeremy Corbyn's Labour Party in 2017 and 2019 (Savage & Vaughan 2024). Criticism has been notably directed toward right-wing parties accused of co-opting the inequality discourse after 2015, reframing it as an issue affecting the 'white' working class—a group portrayed as 'left behind' and 'ignored' (Savage & Vaughan 2024). This rhetoric supports policies like the "levelling up agenda" introduced in the 2019 Conservative Party manifesto (Conservative Party Manifesto 2019, p. 26). However, the extent to which this is solely a right-wing issue may be overstated. In 2020, area-based inequalities in income and wealth were the only forms of inequality about which both Labour (67%) and Conservative voters (59%) expressed comparably high levels of concern—a concern that cuts across Brexit divides (Benson 2021).

More likely, since 2016, longstanding ambiguities about the nature of and solutions to economic inequality have hardened into divisions in public opinion with political consequences. When the British public was surveyed in 2020 about the most serious inequalities in the country, approximately one-third of the population favoured structural explanations, viewing social mobility as compromised by factors beyond individual control—such as family wealth and disparities in education quality (Benson 2021). Another third strongly rejected the influence of factors like family wealth, race, and religion. The remaining third were largely neutral, seldom considering any explanations as 'essential' or 'not at all' important for social mobility, and perceiving society as neither 'very equal' nor 'unequal' (Benson 2021).

Radical changes in employment and household costs resulting from global events like the COVID-19 pandemic and the war in Ukraine have further complicated the discourse. As is common during pandemics (Joffe 2011), the public sought to distance themselves from those affected by attributing harm to perceived individual failings (Phillips & Cassidy 2024). For example, drawing on meritocratic beliefs, Conservative voters (57%) were more likely than Labour voters (39%) to attribute COVID-related job losses to poor performance at work (Benson 2021). Moreover, while movements like Black Lives Matter shifted the discourse on inequality to focus on racial discrimination (Barling 2022; Savage & Vaughan 2024), acceptance of these issues has not been unanimous, nor is there confidence that effective action can be taken (Pereira et al. 2024).

Interim Summary

Scholars have proposed perceptual explanations for the apparent disconnect between the actual levels of economic inequality and the lack of political demands for further redistribution in liberal democratic welfare states. Traditional public opinion methodologies,

based on a unitary epistemology, suggest that the conditions created by high levels of economic inequality led to its non-recognition. These methods affirm beliefs in the fairness of the status quo and categorize groups into "deserving" and "undeserving," attributing these distinctions to inherent differences that bias perception.

However, theories of social representation and communication—primarily derived from media studies—challenge the assumption that these perceptions are self-reproducing. While acknowledging public concerns about fairness related to economic inequality, these theories do not attribute such beliefs to abstract moral philosophy. Instead, they suggest that these beliefs provide opportunities for the formation of distinctive in-group identities, tied to their unique motivations within a competitive political economy. This process may not operate in a continuous, self-maintaining fashion but rather occurs in waves and triggering moments that can both build momentum and lead to fatigue. Consequently, representations of economic inequality and redistribution are shaped by both the content and the process of their communication. Secondly, the promotion of these concerns is not solely related to economic inequality in the abstract but involves ambiguities—particularly between equality of opportunity and equality of outcomes. These ambiguities allow historically enduring stereotypes of the "undeserving" and "dependent free-riders" to persist through stigmatization. Thirdly, sustaining the advancement of concerns about economic inequality often involves attributing blame, although who is held responsible may be uncertain, varied, and subject to contestation.

While the literature discussed thus far suggests political consequences it remains unclear how, or even if, political groups can harness representations of economic inequality to offer redistributive solutions. Methodologically, applying the dynamic epistemology offered by theories of social representations suggests: (1) Investigating the ambiguities through which

economic inequality is understood in the contextual process of communication, with particular focus on equality of opportunity versus equality of outcomes; (2) Observing when, who, and how political groups advance or retreat in their visions of economic inequality; (3) Analysing what representations of economic inequality and proposed redistribution solutions offer for the formation of distinctive group identities, and understanding the relational processes through which oppositional group representations are maintained, often centred around attributing blame.

3. Data Collection

3.1. Corpora Construction:

We collected UK General Election party manifestos from mainstream parties between 2005 and 2024. These manifestos were retrieved in PDF format from the Manifesto Project or the Internet Archive, which archives historical versions of party websites. National elections occurred in 2005, 2010, 2015, 2017, 2019, and 2024. We included the major parties based on the number of Members of Parliament (MPs) elected to the House of Commons: the Conservative and Unionist Party (Conservatives), the Labour Party, the Scottish National Party (SNP), and the Liberal Democrats (LibDems). During this period, Labour and the Conservatives were consistently the two largest parties, while the LibDems and SNP alternated as the third and fourth largest parties. This selection captured between 94.7% and 97% of MPs elected to Parliament.

Our corpus comprised 24 manifestos totalling 527,576 words, with individual manifesto lengths ranging from 8,120 to 35,115 words and an average of 26,379 words (see Appendices 1 and 2). Since manifesto lengths varied over time and between parties, keyword frequencies were normalized by manifesto length.

Each manifesto was retained in its original PDF format to preserve the layout, images, and text formatting (e.g., sizing, italics, colouring, bolding) for subsequent qualitative analysis in MAXQDA 24. The text was extracted using TextEditor and processed in a Python 3 natural language processing environment. Standard preprocessing steps included removing standalone numbers (e.g., page and section numbers), eliminating non-alphabetic characters (e.g., punctuation marks, special characters), normalizing whitespace for consistent word spacing, and converting all text to lowercase. English stop-words were removed using standard NLTK packages, and we manually checked the effects of preprocessing. For each party and election year, the text was concatenated into a single continuous string and segmented into chunks of exactly 50 words.

3.2. Measures:

3.2.1. Economic Inequality Keywords

Keywords representing the concept of economic inequality were informed by McGovern et al. (2023), which traces the development of economic inequality semantics in the UK and USA between 1990 and 2015. According to McGovern, these semantics encompass discussions of economics (e.g., salary, wage, compensation, pay) and inequality (e.g., inequality, distribution, differentials). A co-occurrence analysis revealed that 'inequality' and 'equality' are commonly associated, so we included 'equality' as a search term (Appendix 4). The full list of keywords are provided in Appendix 5. We analysed the data by examining whether both categories of 'economics' and 'inequality' appeared within a 50-word span, coded

as a binary True/False variable. Frequency tables of 'economic inequality' in raw and normalized forms are available in Appendices 6 and 7, respectively.

3.2.2. Redistribution Keywords

To identify keywords related to policy instruments for redistribution, we utilized the House of Commons Library pages on welfare and pensions (accessed on 03.06.2024). The data spans from 09.04.1998 to 29.05.2024 and is publicly available at [House of Commons Library](#). We extracted words indicating mechanisms for redistribution, including various social welfare benefits and support schemes in the UK—such as allowances, pensions, support payments, grants, and tax credits. These programs address diverse needs, from disability and unemployment support to child and family assistance, ensuring financial aid and essential services for different population segments. We cross-referenced search terms against party programs to verify relevance and identify supplementary terms. Efforts were made to include full names and acronyms (e.g., JSA for Job Seeker's Allowance) and to account for linguistic changes in policy names (e.g., the Coronavirus Job Retention Scheme or the replacement of 'Job Seeker's Allowance' with 'Universal Credit'). The full list of terms is available in Appendix 5. Frequency tables of redistribution in raw and normalized forms are provided in Appendices 8 and 9, respectively.

3.2.3. GINI Coefficient

To explore potential relationships between semantic trends and an objective measure of inequality, we included Gini coefficient scores—a common measure of economic inequality for countries, represented as a percentage from 0 (perfect equality) to 100 (perfect inequality).

Data on the UK's Gini coefficient from 1977 to 2022 are produced by the Office for National Statistics, UK (Clark 2024). We produced tables of Gini coefficients for financial year ends (FYE) 2005 to 2022, including year-on-year percentage changes (Appendix 10).

3.2.4. Analytic Strategy

We employed an exploratory convergent mixed-methods triangulation research design, simultaneously considering interpretations suggested by both qualitative and quantitative components (Flick 2018). Both analyses were supported by keyword analysis of 'economic inequality' and 'redistribution,' as outlined in Sections 2.2.1 and 2.2.2. For the quantitative analysis, we transformed these keywords into measures of semantic frequency, normalized by the length of the manifestos, enabling trend analysis by party over time.

In parallel, we recontextualized keywords within party programs for qualitative analysis. This involved a detailed examination of segments identified through the keyword search, applying thematic analysis principles as outlined by Joffe (2011a). We progressed through open, axial, and selective coding to identify underlying patterns in the representation of economic inequality and redistribution. Special attention was given to latent forms of representation, including symbolic imagery, affective language, and structural elements like headings and subheadings. Research quality was ensured through transparent presentation of results, including close readings of extended verbatim quotes. Qualitative data analysis was performed using MAXQDA 24, concluding upon reaching theoretical saturation (Joffe 2011a). As measures of quality in mixed-methods research, we emphasized reflexivity, particularly the capacity to refine and propose new interpretations through the creative integration of qualitative and quantitative components (Flick 2018).

Integration of results was established through triangulation, with quantitative and qualitative analyses developed in parallel and given equal weight in interpretation. The synthesized results were reused to reconsider and refine interpretations in each component.

4. Results

To aid comprehension, we briefly summarize the results, which we will develop in full below. Trend analyses did not show that the semantics of economic inequality or mechanisms for redistribution paralleled changes in national-level objective indicators, nor were the semantics of inequality and redistribution communicated together. Qualitative analysis found that the semantics of economic inequality and redistribution contributed to three interrelated themes: (1) belief in equality of opportunity; (2) common life-course narratives; and (3) distance-blame-stigma patterns. Synthesizing the results, we observe that the salient politicization of the functions of the British welfare state offered political parties the opportunity to develop a distinctive political identity related to broader issues of the day. They attempted to foster a connected public identity, maintained by distancing, blaming, and stigmatizing perceived an ambiguous grouping of political competitors and perceived malign groups in society.

4.1. 'Equality of Opportunity' or 'Equality of outcome'

These results suggest that narratives about "equality of opportunity" regularly develop the semantics of "economic inequality," both reproducing and challenging normative beliefs about desired ways of life within the British welfare state.

In figure 1 we plot changes in the relative salience of economic inequality semantics in party manifestos between election cycles between 2005 and 2024.

Figure 1: UK 2005 - 2024 Semantic Trends in Economic Inequality Normalised by Manifesto Length Plotted Against FYE GINI Coefficients

Figure 1 shows that the salience of economic inequality semantics fluctuates independently of objective changes in economic inequality, as measured by the Gini coefficient. No parties significantly increased references to economic inequality in the 2010 election compared to 2005, despite the 2008 global financial crisis. Furthermore, spikes in attention by opposition parties occurred in different election cycles: the SNP in 2015, while Labour's attention remained low until the 2017 and 2019 elections. Additionally, despite persistently high inequality in 2022, the salience of economic inequality semantics was low across all parties in 2024.

The generally low frequency of economic inequality semantics in party manifestos, along with the disconnect between language and objective measures, may stem from ambiguities in conceptualizing the issue. Even when economic inequality is discussed, the

emphasis tends to be on fostering individual equality of opportunity rather than implementing structural changes to ensure equality of outcomes across electoral cycles.

From 2005 to 2024, we observe recurring representations that use economic inequality semantics to reaffirm the belief that British society provides conditions for equality of opportunity, enabling individuals to strive for social mobility free from group-based discrimination. This representation is largely consistent across the political spectrum. In the 2005 Conservative Party Manifesto (p. 3), "fair play" is constructed as "being treated equally is a birthright, and discrimination is wrong. A Conservative Government will govern in the interests of everyone in our society—black or white, young or old, straight or gay, rural or urban, rich or poor" (ibid). This notion of fairness is mirrored by the Labour Party in 2024, which argues for the need to "level the playing field" (Labour Party Manifesto 2024, p. 31). Moreover, the Labour Party's third "mission" is to "**[b]reak down barriers to opportunity**" (emphasis original; Labour Party Manifesto 2024, p. 13).

Our results confirm that meritocratic and fairness beliefs influence concerns about economic inequality, but they do not support attributing these beliefs to a universal moral framework, as unitary approaches assume. Although notions of what is considered "fair" or "correct" are regularly reaffirmed in political communication to uphold the cultural belief in equality of opportunity, we find that this is not a stable feature of communication. Instead, it is continuously reproduced in political discourse, making the belief in equality of opportunity a subject of contestation. For instance, we observe that references to economic inequality peaked in 2019 under Jeremy Corbyn's leadership of the Labour Party (see Figure 1). At this time, the Labour Party challenged the emphasis on equality of opportunity in favour of structural changes aimed at achieving "justice" as equality of outcome.

"The true measure of fairness is not social mobility but social justice. Implicit in the notion of social mobility is the idea that poverty and inequality are acceptable provided some people can climb the social ladder. Social justice, on the other hand, demands that we end poverty, reduce inequality and create a society in which the conditions for a fulfilling life are available to everyone." (Labour Party Manifesto 2019, p. 64)

Throughout the corpus, references to economic inequality, social mobility, and discrimination were often ambiguous. However, in the above quote, the Labour Party explicitly separates social mobility from inequality. They argue that the implicit alignment among social mobility, inequality, and poverty is incorrect, unacceptable, and unfair. Yet even in this rare instance, we still detect an underlying concern for equality of opportunity through their focus on creating the "conditions" for a "fulfilling life."

4.2. Life-course narratives and redistribution

Previously, we described how normative beliefs about life in the British welfare state were framed in terms of individual equality of opportunity, promoting social mobility free from group-based discrimination. We now focus on the mechanisms of the British welfare state that enable redistributive policies. We find that redistribution is represented not abstractly in terms of income or wealth but through normative visions of the life course. These visions are defined by implied and interconnected constructions of valued and devalued life stages and groups. Furthermore, we demonstrate that the societal construction of groups, communicated through the mechanisms of the welfare state, offered political gain by co-constructing a distinctive identity for political parties with an identity in the electorate.

Our findings indicate that despite the national economic inequality depicted in Figure 2, discourse on the welfare state's redistributive mechanisms does not automatically emerge, even among left-leaning political parties.

Figure 2: UK 2005 - 2024 Semantic Trends in Redistribution Normalised by Manifesto Length Plotted Against FYE GINI Coefficients

Following the widening of economic inequality in 2008, we observe an increase in discussions about the welfare state's redistributive mechanisms in all mainstream party manifestos for the 2010 election. However, we do not find consistent links between objective inequality and these discussions. The Labour Party, representing the political left, showed elevated references to these themes until 2019 but retreated from them by 2024, despite minimal changes in objective conditions. Similarly, the SNP's focus on the welfare state's redistributive mechanisms peaked in the 2017 general election but was largely absent by 2024.

As shown in Table 1, discussions about the welfare state's redistributive mechanisms rarely directly also address economic inequality.

Table 1: UK 2005 - 2024 Both Economic Inequality and Redistribution Semantic Frequency

Year	Conservative	Labour	LibDem	SNP
2005	2	1	2	0
2010	1	0	0	0
2015	0	0	0	2
2017	1	0	0	3
2019	0	1	1	1
2024	0	0	2	1

We interpret this disconnect by qualitatively examining the semantics surrounding these mechanisms. Rather than being a consistent element of political ideology focused on economic inequality, these discussions seem to offer opportunities for political gain during elections. Specifically, parties formed distinctive identities by emphasizing valued life-course narratives that distinguish between interconnected valued and devalued groups and life stages.

Discussions about the welfare state's redistributive mechanisms were framed through life-course narratives that distinguished between valued and devalued groups and life stages. These communications provided opportunities for political strategies that linked party identity with public identity constructions. The narratives employed normative constructions of valued and unvalued groups, emphasizing the centrality of "working families" and "dignified pensioners" in the "British Dream" (Conservative Party Manifesto 2005, p. 3). In 2005, the Conservative Party released a manifesto titled "The British Dream" (p. 3), which emphasized individual opportunities for social mobility and freedom from discrimination, rather than focusing narrowly on wealth or income distribution:

“For me the heart of politics is all about people – their hopes and aspirations. People want the freedom, security and opportunity to get on in life. They want the freedom to take the important decisions about their families and to keep more of the money they earn. They want the security that goes with owning your home, saving for your retirement, living in a safe neighbourhood. They want the opportunity provided by a good education and a thriving economy”.

(Conservative Party Manifesto 2005, p. 1)

The normative individual strives for upward social mobility or to "get ahead in life," achieved through responsible choices and commitments in saving and family life—especially homeownership, contributing to retirement, and promoting neighbourhood safety. These goals are grounded in a *"good education"* and a *"thriving economy."*

Representations of the British dream divided social groups into valued and devalued categories, notably emphasizing "dignified pensioners" and "working families." This showed remarkable consensus across parties and electoral cycles in valuing these normative groups within the imagined life course. In 2005, the Conservative Party argued that Labour policies were failing working families and continued in 2010 to state: "A Conservative government will make Britain the most family-friendly country in Europe" (Conservative Party Manifesto 2010, p. 35). Similarly, the Labour Party claimed to have adapted the welfare state to promote families: "The welfare state simply did not understand working women and families. Today, with family-friendly working and better childcare, it has at last begun to do so" (Labour Party Manifesto 2010, p. 3). This rhetoric remained consistent. The Labour Party declared in 2015 and 2017: "Older people deserve to live a fulfilling life" (2015, p. 49) and "Dignity for pensioners" (2017, p. 54). Likewise, the Conservative Party campaigned in 2019 and 2024 on "ensuring that older people have the security and dignity they deserve" (2019, p. 16), and

presented "Our plan to cut taxes and protect pensions... Our plan to support families... Our plan to get more people into work and build a fairer welfare system" (2024, p. 1).

Normative life-course groups were not viewed neutrally or in isolation. Instead, the need to protect the dignity and security of pensioners and families was contrasted with the distrust attached to stigmatized groups, often expressed through symbols of protection. For example, using the symbol of the "lock," the Labour Party remains committed to "keep the triple-lock so that the state pension increases by inflation" (Labour Party Manifesto 2024, p. 79). This emphasis is set against groups blamed for a "broken society" (Conservative Party Manifesto 2010, viii) and the "scars of inequality" (Liberal Democratic Party Manifesto 2005, p. 2). In the 2010 Conservative Party manifesto, the welfare state's failure was partly attributed to a so-called "underclass" of "welfare dependants" (2010, p. 56), "ASBOs" (p. 56), and "economic migrants" (p. 21). Yet valued groups were also portrayed as being under threat from a hidden elite. For example, the Conservative Party promised to:

“change Britain with a sweeping redistribution of power: from the state to citizens; from the government to Parliament; from Whitehall to communities; from Brussels to Britain; from bureaucracy to democracy. Taking power away from the political elite and handing it to the man and woman in the street” (Conservative Party Manifesto 2010, p.63).

In this, the elite is conceptualised in terms of non-elected ‘bureaucracy’, such as the UK civil service (e.g., ‘Whitehall,’ ‘government’) and European Union (EU) (e.g., ‘Brussels’). ‘Democracy,’ in contrast, is characterised by entities that individuals feel should have control, such as ‘parliament,’ ‘communities,’ and ‘Britain’.

4.3. Distance-Blame-Stigma Patterns

We previously observed that discourse on the welfare state's redistributive functions often involves representations of a normative life course, divided between desired and undesired constructed groups. Changes in how prominently parties discussed these redistributive functions did not directly correspond to changes in objective national indicators of economic inequality, nor were they consistently linked to subjective perceptions of inequality.

In this section, we delve into a common political strategy of distance, blame, and stigma. We found that during key political moments, discourse on the welfare state's redistributive mechanisms offered opportunities for political gain. By identifying a group to blame, political parties could position themselves as uniquely capable of addressing issues hindering the realization of the normative life course.

This strategy involves constructing themselves as the means to achieve the normative life course in the British welfare state by identifying a distant group, devaluing them as the cause of unfairness, and blaming them. This approach helps form a distinctive in-group identity related to the perceived issues of the electoral cycle, setting the party apart from political competitors. To illustrate this, we have quoted the introductory sections of three manifestos with the highest relative frequencies of redistribution semantics (see Appendix 9):

“The Tories have enforced deep spending cuts, they’ve imposed Brexit and have worsened the cost of living crisis. They need to go. But we have to take care about what replaces them – the answer is not more spending cuts. It is not more Brexit and it is definitely not more Westminster decision-making about Scotland. And yet that is what the Labour Party is committed to: cuts, Brexit and continued Westminster control.” (SNP Manifesto 2017, p.3)

“The choice could not be clearer at this election. Labour will put wealth and power in the hands of the many. Boris Johnson’s Conservatives will look after the privileged few” (Labour Party Manifesto 2019, p.8)

“Doesn’t it make you angry that after 65 years of red-blue government, a child’s chances in life are still more determined by their parents’ bank balance than by their own hopes and dreams? Doesn’t it make you angry that the banks have been allowed to ride roughshod over our economy, and are still handing out bonuses by the bucket load?” (Liberal Democrat Manifesto 2010, p.3)

Across the corpus the largest relative frequency of semantics on the redistributive functions of the welfare state are found in SNP 2017 manifesto. As the quote revealed at this moment, following the failure of the Scottish independence referendum and the success of the Brexit referendum, SNP distanced themselves from Westminster, a group characterised as foreign both in physical distance but also political distance, such that people considered to inhabit it, the Conservative and Labour parties, are stigmatised for their support for austerity and blamed for the worsening in costs of living. We find commonalities in the Liberal democrats manifesto in 2010. As alluded by criticism of banker’s bonuses, the liberal democrats distanced themselves from constructed labours and conservative parties handling of the 2008 financial crash, and the perceived failures to realise an equality in opportunity. In addition, these distance-blame-stigma patterns are also indicated in Labour party’s 2019 manifesto, distancing themselves from the constructed malign interests of the conservative party, blaming and tarnishing it for its constructed accumulation of power.

This paper critically explored what applying a dynamic epistemology offers to the study of representations of economic inequality and redistribution, contrasting it with the static epistemology regularly involved in studies of public opinion, using British political party programming as an example. We will now discuss how the empirical contributions made through this paper relate to establishing ecological validity in forming causal explanations of political behaviour concerning economic inequality and redistribution.

5.1. Public Opinion

We find parallels between our findings and the public opinion literature on perceptions of economic inequality and redistribution. Our results expand on the well-established finding that public perceptions of economic inequality or concerns for redistribution, under conditions of high levels of economic inequality in the UK, diverge from objective indicators (Trump 2018; Jachimowicz et al. 2023; Knell & Stix 2020). We found that concern for these concepts in political communication, as contained in political programming, also does not align with objective indicators. Our results support the relevance of meritocracy beliefs to perceptions of inequality and redistribution (Trump 2018; Cavallé 2023) and affirm the importance of group-based beliefs in considerations of economic distribution and the role of the welfare state in addressing these distributions. Specifically, the maintenance of a positive group identity is functional to the construction of stigmatizing representations of an oppositional group identity (Wichowsky & Condon 2020).

However, our results challenge the notion that political behaviour concerning economic inequality and redistribution is self-maintaining. The widening of objective economic

inequality is thought to trigger psychological processes leading to its misrecognition—particularly a desire to perceive one's own position and the social, economic, and political systems as fair or correct—consequently failing to achieve public demand for greater redistribution (Cavaillé 2023; Gobel & Carvacho 2024; Trump 2018). In contrast, we find that, at moments responding to changing party strategy, parties explicitly positioned the status quo as failing to deliver a fair society and normative life experiences to the public. Moreover, instead of weak demands for redistribution being directly related to misperceptions of economic inequality (Gobel & Carvacho 2024), we found a lack of connection between the semantics of economic inequality and the redistributive functions of the welfare state. This suggests that people may maintain multiple perceptions through political communications, rather than misperceptions per se (Bauer & Gaskell 2008; Pereira et al. 2024).

The possibility of a plurality of perceptions, and the centrality of representations of the normative life course, suggest the need for alternative data points that are sensitive to the public expectation of experiencing desired life-course trajectories, rather than a continued narrow focus on explaining the differences between objective and subjective measures of economic inequality. In particular, it may be instructive to pay close attention to the political correlates of beliefs in opportunities for social mobility and concerns about barriers presented by discrimination, especially beliefs in opportunities for education, family life, and homeownership (Benson et al. 2021; Pereira et al. 2024). In this approach, a relational perspective should be taken (Wichowsky & Condon 2020), considering these perceptions not as separable from the groups attributed as ensuring or compromising the realization of these life-course trajectories. Thus, the variable groups held to blame (e.g., "economic migrants," "EU bureaucrats") form the basis for making demands on the redistributive functions of the welfare state. In addition, while economic inequality constitutes an objective reality, its effects may be secondary to more direct influences on the experience of everyday living, such as

changes in the affordability of housing, access to healthcare, and quality of education—central features of the cost of living in the UK (Harari et al. 2022).

5.2. Dynamic Approaches to Political Behaviour

Our results affirm the methodological imperative of multiple data streams, in contrast to the current research program in economic inequality perceptions, which is concerned singularly with measurement refinements in survey-based research (Jachimowicz et al. 2023). While we similarly offer new directions in measurement, we acknowledge that by itself this is insufficient. Fundamentally, models of political behaviour based on decontextualized survey-based research lack ecological validity (Bauer & Gaskell 2008), as they fail to sufficiently address the current uncertainties in the British public regarding the causes and solutions for economic inequality.

As set out in the introduction, scholarship has shown that the public is regularly uncertain whether economic inequality is a "fact of life" (Pereira et al. 2024, p. i90) or at a record high. Moreover, 45% now say they "almost never" trust governments of any party to place the needs of the nation above the interests of their own political party (Montagu & Maplethorpe 2024). Our results suggest that what emerges as public opinion should be interpreted as the product of a politicisation process that did not develop uniformly. Instead, party-specific strategies advanced the issue for political gain following the 2008 Global Financial Crash, without concurrently offering solutions for structural change, and then de-politicised the issue over time, reducing confidence in the causes of and possibilities for addressing economic inequality.

This invites a critical reassessment of the so-called "golden period" of inequality discourse between 2010 and 2015 (Savage & Vaughan 2024, p. 184). Specifically, it highlights

the risks over time posed by promoting public concern for the issue of economic inequality if change on the issue is not realized. Our results expand on the proposition that the post-2008 Global Financial Crash offered a moment for the political and media left and liberal groups to form distinctive identities through criticisms of economic inequality and the role of the welfare state in addressing it. This momentum built up in 2010, and after the electoral failures of the Labour Party under the leadership of Jeremy Corbyn in 2017 and 2019, these concerns had lost momentum by the 2024 election (McGovern et al. 2023; Savage & Vaughan 2024).

We similarly find that the positioning of the Labour Party on issues of economic inequality and redistribution does not neatly relate to a coherent ideological preference—contrary to the assumption that parties of the political left (e.g., Labour) are inherently critical of economic inequality or promote further redistribution accordingly. Rather, while the 2008 Global Financial Crisis likely promoted a politicisation of the redistributive functions of the welfare state, it was only after the party leadership change from Ed Miliband to Jeremy Corbyn that economic inequality increased in salience in political programming, remaining elevated until the change of leadership to Sir Keir Starmer in advance of the 2024 election.

Even as economic inequality belatedly became a feature of Labour party manifestos in 2017 and 2019, the party did not significantly and directly connect the redistributive functions of the welfare state to economic inequality, as segments containing both semantics remained rare. Moreover, when opposition parties have politicised the issue of economic inequality and the perceived failures of the redistributive features of the welfare state, collectively they fail to encode with certainty a simple set of causes. Instead, they focus blame on a variable group defined not strictly by their accumulation of income or wealth but by their status as holding an undeserved accumulation of power. The group to blame could simultaneously constitute an underclass of the undeserving poor (e.g., ASBO recipients) and the undeserving rich ("Westminster politicians")

6. Final Reflections.

Throughout this paper, we have critically engaged with models of political behaviour concerning perceptions of economic inequality and redistributive demands. We contrasted the theoretical and methodological considerations offered by approaches rooted in a static epistemology—common in studies of public opinion—with those of a dynamic epistemology, more developed in the literature on media representations.

By developing research procedures grounded in a dynamic epistemology and applying them to a corpus of British political programming, we challenge models proposed in public opinion research—principally, the proposition that the objective conditions of economic inequality have a self-maintaining relationship with its perception and belief in its fairness. Instead, our study suggests that while there is largely consensus on the basis for thinking about issues of inequality and the redistributive functions of the welfare state—sustained through representations of the normative life course—these motivations are not fixed in character. Rather, they are maintained and shaped through political communication. Political parties may harness these motivations at varying time points to advance political strategy, developing a distinctive party identity connected to the desires of the electorate, holding an alternative group to blame, and positioning themselves as uniquely capable of addressing the issues.

We expanded on the methodological implications of this paper for future research, providing directions for studies in public opinion. Specifically, we advocate for the use of a diverse array of novel data sources more closely related to the foundations of public thinking on the issue in British public opinion. We also offer guidance on the interpretation of data sets, particularly emphasizing the need to interpret results as part of a synthesis. This approach allows us to understand the current state of uncertainty and multiple explanations in public

opinion, partly due to the political communications through which these opinions may have been formed.

By critically challenging the notion of a self-maintaining character of public opinion, and proposing instead that it is the product of a non-linear politicisation process aimed at political gain, we highlight how concerns over economic inequality have been developed as a distinctive feature of group identity without associated redistributive solutions. While the advancement of economic inequality discourse can be seen as successful in building public concern, it also proposes risks. As the discourse on economic inequality has progressed, it has failed to maintain the public confidence or political trust necessary for needed change. Consequently, economic inequality has been presented as an issue harming society without the belief that solutions can be reasonably found.

7. References

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8. Appendices

Appendix 1: Table of UK Main Party Manifesto Text Lengths in words 2005 - 2024.

Year	Conservative	Labour	Liberal Democrats	Scottish National Party	Year Average
2005	6858	27929	16317	12272	15844

2010	28018	29676	19940	8583	21554
2015	30811	18466	35115	18776	25792
2017	30217	24161	21355	20397	24032
2019	20950	25876	27541	21693	24015
2024	26324	26040	22141	8120	20656
Party Average	23863	25358	23734	14973	

Appendix 2: Graph of UK Main Party Manifesto Text Lengths in words 2005 - 2024.

Appendix 4

Top-10 Words associated with Inequality & Equality in British Party Manifesto 2005 - 2024

Inequality only	Equality only	Inequality or Equality
equality	inequality	poverty
poverty	poverty	opportunity
government	opportunity	sex
people	sex	people
progressive	people	government
reduce	government	country
social	country	tackling
problems	tackling	work
better	work	marriage
family	marriage	children

Appendix 5: Key Words

Economic Inequality Keywords:

Keywords derived from: McGovern, Patrick; Bauer, Martin and Obradovic, Sandra (2023). In search of a Tawney Moment: income inequality, financial crisis and the mass media in the UK and the USA. *The Sociological Review*, 71(5) pp. 1213–1233.

Category: Economic:

Wealth

Income

Economy

Salary

Compensation

Pay

Category: Inequality

Inequality

Equality

Distribution

Differential

Redistribution Keywords:

Attendance Allowance

Additional State Pension

Armed Forces Compensation Scheme

Bereavement Allowance

Bereavement Payment

Bereavement Support Payment

Budgeting Loan

Benefit Cap

Benefit Support for Housing Costs

Carer's Allowance

Carer's Credit

Child Benefit

Child Funeral Fund

Child Maintenance

Child Tax Credits

Christmas Bonus

Cold Weather Payment

Constant Attendance Allowance

Crisis Loans

Cost of Living Payments

Childcare Support for Students

Carer's Leave

Council Tax Reduction Schemes

Coronavirus Job Retention Scheme

Citizens' Rights Provisions

Disability Living Allowance

Disability Benefit Assessments

Discretionary Housing Payments

Domestic Abuse Support

DWP Benefit Sanctions

Employment and Support Allowance

ESA

Early Intervention Policies

Finance Support

Funeral Expenses Payment

Free School Meals Support

Furlough Scheme

Guardians Allowance

Help with Health Costs

Home Responsibilities Protection

Housing Benefit

Housing Benefit Extended Payment

Healthy Start Scheme

High Income Child Benefit Charge

Help with Childcare Costs

Help with Energy Bills

Household Support Fund

Income Support

Independent Living Fund

Industrial Injuries Disablement Benefit

Jobseeker's Allowance

JSA

Local Housing Allowance

LHA

Maternity Allowance

Motability

National Insurance Number

No Recourse to Public Funds

Over 80 Pension

Pension Credit

Personal Independence Payment

PIP

Reduced Earnings Allowance

Redundancy Pay

Rent Safety Net

Severe Disablement Allowance

State Pension

Statutory Adoption Pay

Statutory Maternity Pay

Statutory Paternity Pay

Statutory Sick Pay

SSP

Sure Start Maternity Grant

Support for Mortgage Interest

SMI

Support for Single Parent Families

Social Security

Supported Exempt Accommodation

Tax Credits

Test and Trace Support Payments

Triple-Lock

Universal Credit

Universal Basic Income

Universal Credit Uplift

Universal Credit Assessment Period and Earned Income

War Disablement Pension

War Widow or Widower's Pension

Widowed Parent's Allowance

Winter Fuel Payment

Working Tax Credit

Work Capability Assessment

Appendix 6: Economic Inequality Semantic Frequency

Year	Conservative	Labour	LibDem	SNP
2005	3	5	7	4
2010	13	6	5	0
2015	6	5	15	16
2017	10	19	10	11
2019	1	24	16	9
2024	3	6	8	2

Appendix 7: Economic Inequality Semantic Frequency Normalised by Manifesto Length *100

Year	Conservative	Labour	LibDem	SNP
2005	0.0437	0.0179	0.0429	0.0326
2010	0.0464	0.0202	0.0251	0.0
2015	0.0195	0.0271	0.0427	0.0852
2017	0.0331	0.0786	0.0468	0.0539
2019	0.0048	0.0928	0.0581	0.0415
2024	0.0114	0.023	0.0361	0.0476

Appendix 8: Redistribution Semantic Frequency

Year	Conservative	Labour	LibDem	SNP
2005	11	13	9	5
2010	12	25	22	5
2015	27	20	32	33
2017	24	26	22	49
2019	12	30	14	46
2024	22	10	23	3

Appendix 9: Redistribution Semantic Frequency Normalised by Manifesto Length *100

Year	Conservative	Labour	LibDem	SNP
2005	0.01604	0.0465	0.0552	0.0407
2010	0.0428	0.0842	0.1103	0.0583
2015	0.0876	0.1083	0.0911	0.1758
2017	0.0794	0.1076	0.103	0.2402
2019	0.0573	0.1159	0.0508	0.212
2024	0.0836	0.0384	0.1039	0.0369

Appendix 10: Year-by-Year Changes in GINI Coefficients to two decimal points FYE 2005 – 2022

Year	GINI	Year-on-Year Change (%)
2004/05	34.3	
2005/06	35.9	1.6
2006/07	37.0	1.1
2007/08	38.6	1.6
2008/09	35.6	-3.0
2009/10	36.6	1.0

2010/11	34.1	-2.5
2011/12	33.8	-0.3
2012/13	34.4	0.6
2013/14	35.3	0.9
2014/15	34.7	-0.6
2015/16	35.1	0.4
2016/17	33.4	-1.7
2017/18	35.0	1.6
2018/19	36.0	1.0
2019/20	35.4	-0.6
2020/21	34.4	-1.0
2021/22	35.7	1.3